

Effects of calving interval of dairy cows on development, metabolism and milk performance of their offspring

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This paper includes 1 supplementary table and 2 supplementary figures.

Supplementary Table S1. Milk feeding schedule

Supplementary Figure S1A-I. Body weight and plasma metabolites from birth to calving of offspring from dairy cows with different calving interval (CInt) (CInt_1: 324 - 408 d; CInt_2: 409 - 468 d; CInt_3: 469 - 586 d)

Supplementary Figure S1a-i. Body weight and plasma metabolites from birth to weaning of offspring from dairy cows with different calving interval (CInt) (CInt_1: 324 - 408 d; CInt_2: 409 - 468 d; CInt_3: 469 - 586 d)

Supplementary Figure S2. Body condition, plasma metabolites, and milk performance during the first 100 DIM after calving of offspring from dairy cows with different calving interval (CInt) (CInt_1: 324 - 408 d; CInt_2: 409 - 468 d; CInt_3: 469 - 586 d)

Supplementary Table S1. Milk feeding schedule

Phase	Duration	Age (approximately)	Volume	Concentration of milk replacer
On arrival	7 d	3 - 4 wk	4 L/d	175 g/L
Growth phase	28 d	4 - 8 wk	6 L/d	175 g/L
Finishing phase	21 d	8 - 11 wk	6 → 1.5 L/d	150 g/L
Weaning phase	2 d	11 wk	1.5 → 0 L/d	150 g/L

Supplementary Figure S1A

Supplementary Figure S1a

Supplementary Figure S1B

Supplementary Figure S1b

Supplementary Figure S1C

Supplementary Figure S1c

Supplementary Figure S1D

Supplementary Figure S1d

Supplementary Figure S1E

Supplementary Figure S1e

Supplementary Figure S1F

Supplementary Figure S1f

Supplementary Figure S1G

Supplementary Figure S1g

Supplementary Figure S1H

Supplementary Figure S1h

Supplementary Figure S1I

Supplementary Figure S1i

Supplementary Figure S2A

Supplementary Figure S2B

Supplementary Figure S2C

Supplementary Figure S2D

Supplementary Figure S2E

Supplementary Figure S2F

Supplementary Figure S2G

Supplementary Figure S2H

Supplementary Figure S2I

Supplementary Figure S2J

Supplementary Figure S2K

Supplementary Figure S2L

Supplementary Figure S2M

Supplementary Figure S2N

Supplementary Figure S20

Supplementary Figure S2P

Supplementary Figure S2Q

Supplementary Figure S2R

